

**THE CHALLENGES OF HEALTH EDUCATION IN SUPERVISION
ACTIONS: THE REALITY OF THE MUNICIPALITY OF MIRACEMA
DO TOCANTINS-TO**

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ABSTRACT

We seek to address the role of Sanitary Surveillance acting in defense and promotion of health through Sanitary Education and Permanent Education. We start from the principle that it is necessary to instigate the population towards issues related to their health and for the good of the community. Continuing education permeates the trajectory of health promotion, as it comprises the sharing of knowledge capable of promoting a change in the dynamics of the teamwork process. The article presents a brief discussion on health education in the face of the Coronavirus pandemic that has spread in the country, devastating lives, causing a collapse in the public health system, in the supply of goods and services and in the social life of individuals. The challenge is to give visibility to health actions not only in the context of the pandemic, but during the work process of Health Inspectors and other health professionals. We highlight the lack of autonomy of the Sanitary Surveillance of Miracema do Tocantins and the devaluation of public servants; We raise the need for municipal managers to understand the importance of the sanitary inspection service, which is not restricted to sanitary licensing, but rather seeks to prevent risks to the environment, workers and the population in general.

Keywords: Health Surveillance. Coronavirus. Health Education.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Brazilian Federal Constitution of 1988 guarantees that health is a universal right regulated by Law n° 8080/90 that creates the Unified Health System (SUS). Thus, the Constitutional Charter declares:

Health is everyone's right and the State's duty, guaranteed through social and economic policies aimed at reducing the risk of disease and other injuries and universal and equal access to actions and services for its promotion, protection and recovery . (Federal Constitution, 1998, art. 196-200)

In order to regulate the structure and functioning of the SUS, Federal Law No. 8080 of September 19, 1990 was approved, the Organic Health Law “[...] which provides for the conditions for the promotion, protection and recovery of health, and the organization and functioning of the corresponding services [...]” . (SUS, 1990, p. 1).

This precept is complemented by Law 8.080/90 in its 2nd article “[...] health is a fundamental human right, and the State must provide the indispensable conditions for its full exercise [...] ”. The highlight of the Law is the definition of Sanitary Surveillance, which corroborates with the strengthening and defense of health promotion, as

[...] a set of actions capable of eliminating, reducing or preventing health risks and intervening in health problems arising from the environment, the production and circulation of goods and the provision of services of interest to health, covering: I- the control of consumer goods that, directly or indirectly, are related to health, including all stages and processes from production to consumption; and II- consumption of services that are directly or indirectly related to health. (SUS, 1990, p 1)

Health surveillance actions represent a privileged space for promoting and guaranteeing the right to health (Campos, 2009, p 10) involving other sectoral policies articulated to prevent risks to the health of the population. In this sense, the scope of Sanitary Surveillance permeates routine inspection actions and dialogues with permanent education in order to instigate the dissemination of knowledge about its field of action. In this regard, Palacio and Takenami (2020, p. 2) state that

[...] Educational practices need to encompass knowledge from both sides – health and education – so that care actions are successful – here it includes prevention, protection, promotion, rehabilitation, palliative care and not just the cure of diseases [...]

As the authors state, health and education form a symbiosis in relation to the process of knowledge and professional qualification as the work processes are conducted in a critical

perspective. Allowing yourself to enter the universe of Permanent Education in Health, training and continuing qualification, encourages professionals to leave their comfort zone and seek strategies to break with pragmatism.

In their daily routine, health professionals need to strip themselves of their beliefs, political convictions and any judgment of moral value that is contrary to their intellectual growth, as the success of actions directly depends on personal and professional motivations. In this sense, it is worth emphasizing the importance of the actions carried out by the Sanitary Inspector, who in their daily lives deal directly with the population.

To corroborate the dialogue about the educational process in public policies, especially those related to health, reiterating the continuity of knowledge of professionals, we have the author's speech:

[...] I emphasize that what should be really central to Permanent Health Education is its porosity to the mutable and changing reality of health actions and services; is its political connection with the formation of professional profiles and services, the introduction of mechanisms, spaces and themes that generate self-analysis, self-management, implication, institutional change, in short, thinking (disruption with institutions, formulas or models) and experimentation (in context, in affectivity – being affected by reality/affection)[...](CECCIM, 2005 p.116)

Dialoguing with renowned authors in the health area, who defend that the permanent education process is guided by ethical-political principles, makes the work environment less doomed to pragmatism. In this vein, health professionals cannot be minimalist, fatalistic or messianic, however, they must conduct their work processes with a conjunctural and dynamic look, considering the challenges posed every day.

The Sanitary Surveillance is a body that acts directly on issues related to the health of the population, not only as a supervisory body, but through educational guidelines in order to inform the population about the risks of consuming or even purchasing a product that is not within norms of food safety, nutrition and/or without origin. In this sense, the Sanitary Surveillance contributes to the promotion of health and the prevention of risks to the community, exercising its role of executing the actions planned and guided by ANVISA

ANVISA aims to "promote the health of the population, through sanitary control, production and commercialization of products and services subject to Sanitary Surveillance (ANVISA, 1999).

According to Lucchese (2008, p.245),

Health surveillance, as instituted in Brazil, encompasses the regulation of a very wide range of products and services, of a diverse nature, grouped into the main branches: food; of medicines; biological products, such as vaccines and blood derivatives; medical, dental, hospital and laboratory products; of sanitizers and disinfectants; of personal hygiene products, perfumes and cosmetics, in addition to the sanitary control of ports, airports and border stations and the wide range of services of interest to health.

As stated by Lucchese (2008), the field of action of Health Surveillance is broad, diverse and brings together sectors of health and of interest to health. Due to its regulatory profile, the Sanitary Surveillance imposes its administrative police power through routine inspections, striving for biosafety in health. Common sense ignores the fields of action of the Sanitary Surveillance, attributing responsibility to the sectors of food and health. Such lack of knowledge is understandable, as it brings to light the genesis of Sanitary Surveillance, which was focused only on the health area and had a unilateral and hygienist look. This Sanitary Surveillance bias was modified through the creation of ANVISA and the adoption of measures aimed at promoting the health and well-being of the community.

The professional qualification of the Sanitary Inspector is one of the requirements for sanitary actions to be guided by commitment and ethics. Without prior knowledge of their attributions, the professional is not capable of achieving success in their activities, becoming hostage to minimalist attitudes and falling short of what governs the health policy and the guiding instruments for their performance, as they are, above all, a educator agent and defender of the population's health promotion. The health inspector acts as a channel for disseminating knowledge, through guidelines passed on to the population.

The health inspection service must first act in the prevention and promotion of the health of the user population and, subsequently, apply punitive legislation when necessary. The characteristic of sanitary education must be seen in the actions carried out by the agency and by the health secretariats as a necessary requirement for investiture in the position. Education must first promote awareness and self-assessment in the agent issuing the information (Health Inspector or other professional in the area), as he must understand the meaning of future actions of his educational activity. The effectiveness of the action will depend a lot on the expanded understanding of the benefits promoted by health education, health education.

2 Theoretical foundation

Since their creation, the Sanitary Surveillance regulatory bodies have sought to guide health professionals, public and private institutions and the population in general about the

importance of strict sanitary control over products and services intended for the population, in accordance with ANVISA's mission,

Promote and protect the health of the population, through intervention in the risks arising from the production and use of products and services subject to sanitary surveillance, in a coordinated and integrated action within the scope of the Unified Health System ¹.

Public health has experienced, since the 1990s, a struggle in defense of the quality and free provision of services for the population. The SUS is everyone's achievement, but not everyone has access to the system in an integral and universal way. A harsh reality that over the years has been increasingly evident in the news, internet and other media that publicize the chaos that the country is going through with the scrapping of the public fund, especially with the resources destined to health and education .

Local Sanitary Surveillance has been crucial for the activities scheduled and/or carried out in relation to the sanitary inspection service for the population and for the regulated sector to be effective, however, public managers must be committed to decision-making in relation to the public budget and the planning of each sector.

When it comes to the municipal scope, we have to consider the peculiarities of each region and municipality, since the allocated resources will be according to the population parameter, which may, in some cases, be unfavorable for the residents. In these cases, it is necessary that there be a counterpart from the municipality to complement the sending of funds from the federated entity, which becomes quite time-consuming considering that they are discretionary acts of the municipal management.

The reality of the municipality of Miracema do Tocantins is not an isolated case, the planning of intersectoral actions is carried out only in the sector without maintaining dialogue with the other collaborative entities, it is planning without the participation of the community. Common situations of so many other administrations that administered the municipality acting in their little boxes, isolated and without any effectiveness. As for Social Control, the municipality falls short of expectations as determined by current legislation; they need to be more active in terms of monitoring and monitoring the planning, programming and allocation of public resources to the population.

Drawing a brief summary of health education actions in the municipality, we point out the lack of autonomy of the sectoral managements, since the immediate superiors cannot

¹Available at <http://portal.anvisa.gov.br/institucional> . Accessed on 04/15/2020.

perform a good job without the support of the Municipal Executive and the Municipal Health Secretariat. Both hierarchies must walk in the same direction, without partisanship, but committed to the well-being of the population. Maybe it was like that! So many planned actions that are not carried out due to partisanship, individualism and lack of commitment on the part of managers, disregarding the dedication and professionalism of each sector involved.

2.1 Health Surveillance actions in the fight against COVID-19: challenges in prevention and health promotion

In March 2020, open television news, social networks and other media, spread the advance of a pandemic that was plaguing humanity: the new Coronavirus or as it became better known: COVID- 19 . A virus that has been named by the World Health Organization (WHO) as:

The World Health Organization (WHO) declared, on January 30, 2020, that the outbreak of the disease caused by the new coronavirus (COVID-19) constitutes a Public Health Emergency of International Concern - the Organization's highest level of alert, as provided for in the International Health Regulations. On March 11, 2020, COVID-19 was characterized by the WHO as a pandemic. 6,057,853 cases of COVID-19 (122,917 new compared to the previous day) and 371,166 deaths (4,000 new compared to the previous day) were confirmed worldwide as of June 1, 2020.²

The disease drastically changed people's routine, changing their way of life, social habits, such as leisure, work, school life, food, among others. In turn, measures to prevent, cope with, and control the disease by health defense agencies resulted in drastic consequences, many of which irreversible. The routine in the big cities, marked by the bustle of the big centers, brought a transitory “calm”. The change in the way of life of the population of large centers has led to numerous containment situations, aiming to minimize the advances of the pandemic.

Public health bodies such as ANVISA, WHO and other institutions linked to the defense of health have joined efforts to expand information about the Covid-19 pandemic in order to identify the ways in which the disease is contagious and, in this way, provide information accurate information to the population, an arduous task that required a task force of states, municipalities and the union. Brazil watched the news on a daily basis about the advances of the pandemic and the speed with which it reached the population, decimating innocent lives,

²Available at
https://www.paho.org/bra/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=6101:covid19&Itemid=875.
Accessed on 6/2/2020.

exposed to the virus and thus spreading faster. The conditions favorable to the spread of the virus, added to people's lack of awareness, disobeying the social isolation campaigns propagated since the beginning of the pandemic's advance.

During the pandemic, the health inspection service in the municipality achieved coverage rates much higher than the work routine. Sanitary inspectors carried out educational blitzes at night, seeking to avoid crowds in commercial establishments through sanitary guidelines, initially of an educational nature. There were two years of many night blitzes on weekends, the blitzes were carried out with the support of other bodies, such as: military police, civil police, criminal police, inspection of the municipality's attitude and epidemiological surveillance. Due to the ostensive conduct of the other bodies supporting the action, we knew that we would encounter resistance from the owners of the establishments, but it was necessary that the guidelines were passed on, complying with the determination of ANVISA and the Ministry of Health. In addition to the urban area, the work to raise awareness about Covid-19 was intensified in the rural area of the city, in the spas, beaches and hotels, as they are tourist routes in the city, promoting large agglomerations.

The great challenge for health professionals is to sensitize the population about the harmful effects of the disease, sequelae, prevention and forms of transmission, although the vast majority already know about it. The importance of bringing accurate and correct information to people who lack the material conditions and technological tools to better understand the disease are fundamental to combating it.

3. Final Considerations

Our intention was to highlight the performance of health surveillance in the defense of educational actions and health promotion, both in the context of the coronavirus pandemic and any situation that causes health risk. Knowledge through education promotes people's collective awareness and encourages them to leave their comfort zone and expand the barriers imposed by intellectual inertia.

The objective of the work was to disseminate the educational work routine carried out during the covid-19 pandemic, highlighting health surveillance actions, making them known by the population, as an ally in the fight against the proliferation of the virus and ways of preventing the disease. The importance of Sanitary Surveillance in the municipality is extremely relevant, and it must have a physical and human structure to meet local demands, both those within its competence and services of interest to health. Since the publication of

Decree No. 087/2021, the Municipal Health Department has endeavored to comply with the recommendations published by Municipal Decree No. 087/2021, as well as WHO/Ministry of Health/ANVISA determinations. The municipality has only one service enabled to specifically attend to cases of Covid-19, the COVID-19 Service Center (CAC); the UBS are just the rear of the service, being the same used to meet the daily routine of the population.

Professionals who work in the fight against the pandemic must have knowledge of the facts, be qualified and invested in their functions, respecting the principle of ethics and commitment to the population that uses the services.

We could not fail to mention that, like the municipality of Miracema do Tocantins, which did not guarantee the financial valuation of health inspectors compatible with the night work routine, without due salary compensation, such as the payment of the percentage of dangerous work and the payment of overtime, other municipalities also did not recognize the efforts of health professionals in their entirety.

Health surveillance in the exercise of its functions plays a fundamental role in dealing with the Covid 19 pandemic, not only by enforcing health standards through its police power, but also by the numerous health guidelines dispensed to regulated sectors and the general population. Acting in partnership with other agencies to fight the disease, public policy managers, organized civil society, social movements, universities, among other mechanisms for disseminating information and fighting the disease. It is salutary to point out that if there is no transformation in the conception of health as a constitutionally guaranteed right to every citizen, with society having full access to health services available in the community, in its territory, conservative and paternalistic practices will continue to stifle the growth of the country and the advancement of public policies.

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